

SOCIAL MEDIA INFLUENCERS AND THE DIGITAL DEMOCRACY

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ABSTRACT

This research examines how social media influencers shape the political opinions of Filipino netizens. The research employs quantitative and descriptive approach and surveyed 500 respondents selected at random and identified as belonging to generation Z. The survey questionnaire solicited respondents' demographic information, social media platforms actively use, how often they check their favorite social media sites, political influencers they intentionally follow, their most trusted people to learn about politics, and their attitudes on the effects of social media in shaping their political opinion. The results showed that Filipino netizens, particularly generation Z, are active social media users, with most respondents monitoring social media "several times a day". However, most respondents claimed social media negatively affects forming their political opinions, and the most trusted source of information about politics was their family. As suggested, politicians should encourage generation Z to get involved in politics, raise awareness about the importance of political participation, increase the use of social media in promoting political agendas, reduce false and misleading information in social media, ensure social media accessibility, and finally, increase positive media influence. This research refutes the notion that generation Z learns political opinions more through social media than from parents or teachers.

Keywords: *social media influencers, political opinion, democracy*

INTRODUCTION

Social and digital media have reached unparalleled levels of popularity worldwide. It has effectively overcome hurdles in a variety of societal contexts, including politics. With the transition from analog to digital media, the world now has more capacity and resources for people to access, collect, and receive information for both political and recreational purposes.

Social media has grown beyond basic interaction to become a critical battleground for political beliefs and campaigns, giving rise to influencers capable of shaping public opinion on an enormous scale, manipulating public opinion through various communication strategies, and creating disinformation or manipulated media (Oxford, 2021). The explosion of online content and the emergence of new distribution methods have permitted the quick diffusion of both legitimate and disputed information, notably on social media platforms. This leads to the conclusion that social media influencers have become critical players in this new landscape. These influencers, with their vast number of followers, now have the power to influence public opinion, increase political involvement, and even affect electoral outcomes (Frimpong et al., 2020; Rita and Afonso, 2023).

Social media content creators, also known as influencers, have become emblems of ordinary people who have achieved great success. They have a strong voice and challenge established sources of information and knowledge, significantly influencing public opinion (Gerlich, 2023 and Trziszka, 2023). A research carried out after the 2022 national election in the country found that there is an estimated total of 600 million to 1.5 billion was allocated to socio-political influencers who actively campaigned for presidential and vice-presidential candidates (Gaw et al., 2023). The estimated quantity is significant for a political campaign. Social media has a bigger influence than traditional news outlets. When they perceive a credible influence associated with a piece of content, they tend to consider the content as more trustworthy, even if it contains erroneous information (Mena et.al, 2020). Consequently, filtered information is broadly distributed.

Social and digital media platforms, such as Facebook and its subsidiaries, have significantly impacted how political information is disseminated and processed (Edgerly and Thorson, 2020). Influencers now hold significant power and influence due to their big following, allowing them to create and circulate inaccurate information that can significantly impact political views and beliefs. In a research conducted by Goodwin et al. (2021) they observe that candidates without celebrity or influencer support struggled during campaigns. Nowadays, politicians have found digital networks such as Facebook and Twitter to be excellent campaign tools due to their large audience reach.

Today, political candidates are using their websites to engage with the public, encourage donations, recruit volunteers, and convert traditional communications into digital formats such as press releases and television ads (Abbas et.al, 2019). Politicians use it to gain attention online and to demonstrate and advertise their platforms. Candidates can utilize social media to broaden their message, highlight important

advocacy projects, improve accessibility to speeches and remarks, and generate free publicity for their campaigns. It now has the ability to democratically influence the electoral process (Buenaobra, 2016). Political advertising is the use of strategies and gimmicks in online elections. Candidates can reach out to previously uninterested voters by advertising in various media venues. Social media platforms like Facebook and Twitter have transformed political education and campaigning. Vulnerable voters, particularly those who lack political literacy, have the greatest potential to support a candidate's victory.

The objective of this research is to examine how social media influencers shape the political opinions of Filipino netizens particularly the generation Z. It also aims to provide a better understanding of how these influencers shape political discourse and influence political beliefs in the Philippines, as well as emphasizes an important feature of Filipino modern politics.

Research Questions

This research examines how social media influencers shape the political opinions of Filipino netizens. The researchers contend that social media influencers play roles in modern politics, allowing them to act beneath the surface of political involvement in order to weaken or strengthen it, given the political-economic environment in which they operate, which promotes transparency or sometimes manipulation. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of the following:
 - a. Year level
 - b. Gender
2. How do social media influencers shape the political opinions of Filipino netizens specifically the generation Z?
3. What are the effects of social media influencers' engagement with Filipino netizens on shaping their personal political opinions?
4. What recommendations may be made to improve the quality of political discourse as it shapes online discussions and influences netizens' opinions?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The present research used a quantitative-descriptive approach to examine the topic at hand. The initial step in conducting this research was to identify respondents who had a personal grasp of social media influencers and how they currently affect the political system. Second, to address the identified problem, respondents were surveyed at

random. The third phase consists of evaluating the results of surveys and other secondary sources to provide context and background on the particular issue. The collected data is examined using descriptive statistics.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this research are people belonging to Generation Z, ranging in age from 12 to 27 years old, who are active users of any social media platform, are currently attending college or university level program, and are aware of the country's current political situation. Finally, they must consent to participate in the researchers' survey.

Sampling Technique

The researchers used a random sampling technique to obtain the right number of respondents for this research. Random sampling is a probabilistic sampling approach in which respondents are chosen at random from a selected segment of a population. In this sampling technique, every member of the population has an equal chance of being chosen (Cresswell, 2005). There were 500 respondents, 263 males and 237 females from generation Z, all of whom were current university students in various year levels. The survey research approach is appropriate because the research required information from respondents who agreed to be surveyed privately.

Scope and Limitation

This research examines how social media influencers shape the political opinions of Filipino netizens by examining both the influence strategies used and their impact on public political engagement and opinion formation. It also seeks to provide a better understanding of how these influencers drive political discourse and views in the Philippines, as well as to highlight a crucial aspect of Filipino modern politics.

Moreover, it is critical to identify and assess the research's weaknesses. The research is limited to selected university undergraduate students. As a result, the findings cannot be applied to the entire Filipino generation Z in the country. The research also lacks insights and opinions from other young people classified as generation Z who attend various educational institutions and universities around the country and may have had different experiences. As a result, it should be emphasized that the research's scope is limited because it does not cover all conceivable variables for analyzing the impact of social media influencers on Filipino netizens in influencing their personal political opinions.

Data Gathering Method

The researchers sent a letter of permission to the authorities of a certain university where the survey is being done, stating their intention to conduct a survey among its

students. After receiving the consent, they began collecting data from the intended respondents. The researchers gave the respondents a consent form that explained the objective of the research and assured them of their confidentiality.

Data Analysis

To conclude the results of this research, the data provided by respondents was processed and reviewed to produce the hypothesis and answers to research questions. The survey data was electronically processed and summarized to provide descriptive results for analysis and interpretation using the predefined study variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents by year level and gender

Variable	Indicator	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	263	52.6
	Female	237	47.4
Year Level	Freshmen	187	37.4
	Sophomore	82	16.4
	Junior	56	11.2
	Senior	175	35

Table 1 indicates the gender of the respondents, which is 52.6% male and 47.4% female. By year level, 37.4% are freshmen, 16.4% are sophomore, 11.2% are junior, and lastly, 35% are senior.

It may be concluded that the majority of the Filipino netizens surveyed belong to generation Z are male, with the bulk of them being freshmen students. According to the data gathered, most freshmen use social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and etc.

Figure 1. Social Media Platforms Actively Use

Figure 1 shows respondents' preferences for the social media platforms they actively utilize. Out of 500 respondents, 63% utilized Facebook, 8% used Instagram, 9% used YouTube, and 10% used Instagram and Tiktok. According to Statista (n.d), Facebook is the most popular social media network in the Philippines, serving as both a primary source of news and a platform for e-commerce businesses to reach out to potential customers.

Table 2. Frequency of Checking their Favorite Social Media Platforms

Indicator	Frequency	Percentage
Several Times a Day	438	87.6
Once a Day	52	10.4
A Few Times a Week	6	1.2
Once a Week	3	0.6
Less Often	1	0.2

Table 2 shows that most respondents receive their political news through social media. It also shows that 87.6% of generation Z respondents access social media several times a day. These results suggest that generation Z spends significant time and attention on these mediums. Social media is a popular way for generation Z to stay informed about politics. Generation Z prefers social media, but they also have access to traditional forms of media. According to Rahn and Marchand (n.d), generation Z grew up and will continue to grow up in a culture dominated by social media and fast access to information; they are a curious, diverse, and inclusive population. They are a generation that has been and continues to be exposed to a wide variety of viewpoints, beliefs, and lifestyles.

Figure 2. Political Influencers They Intentionally Follow

Figure 2 illustrates that the majority of the respondents surveyed do not intentionally follow any political influencers have 72.1%. Approximately 8% follow 1-2 political influencers, 6.9% follow 3-5 political influencers, 4.3% follow 6-9 political influencers, 5% follow more than ten political influencers, and 3.7% are unaware of any political influencers. However, merely because most respondents do not actively follow political influencers does not imply that they are not frequently exposed to them on social media.

Figure 3. People They Trust to Learn About Politics

Figure 3 illustrates where they trust to learn more about politics, most respondents, 68.7%, said they trust their family members. 14.5% of respondents said they trusted their teachers/professors, 6% trusted social media, 3.2% trusted mass media, 5% trusted their friends/peers, and 2.6% trusted social media influencers.

The survey strives to determine where Filipino netizens, particularly Generation Z, get their political news. When asked who they trust the most to learn about politics, more than half responded to their family members. This data eventually refutes the notion that generation Z learns political opinions more through social media than from parents or teachers. Although the media plays an essential role in changing people's thinking and behavior nowadays, it is reasonable to claim that most people are growing more knowledgeable and conscious of their political participation and process.

Figure 4. Effects of Social Media in Shaping the Political Opinion of the Respondents

Figure 4 shows the effects of social media on their political opinions, 70% of respondents stated it had a negative impact. Positive effects accounted for only 17% of the responses with 13% being neutral.

Table 3. Positive Effects on Shaping the Political Opinions of Respondents

Positive Effect on Shaping the Political Opinion	Frequency	Percentage
Increasing people's knowledge and awareness	135	96.43
Accessibility to news	67	47.86
Communication/connection /community	90	64.2
Exposure to diverse thoughts or perspectives	55	39.29
Advocacy and movements for social change	76	54.29

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Awareness for communities that are marginalized	56	40
Making people or organizations accountable	35	25
Others	22	16.43

In table 3, 140 respondents were asked about the positive effects of social media. Respondents were given a list of reasons why they believe social media positively impacts political opinions. The respondents were given multiple response questions and could select as many answers as they agreed with. Almost all respondents believe social media has a positive effect on shaping political opinions by increasing knowledge and awareness garnering 96.43%. Meanwhile, 64.2% of selected respondents agree on the importance of communication, connection, and community are positive components of social media as well.

Table 4. Negative Effects on Shaping the Political Opinions of Respondents

Negative Effect on Shaping the Political Opinion	Frequency	Percentage
Misinformation, fake news, hatred, extremism, and harassment	313	86.94
People trusting everything, people who have no idea what to believe	260	72.22
Censorship/Bias	178	49.44
Negative effects on mental health.	111	30.83
Excessive discrimination on social media.	73	20.28
People only get a single point of view.	35	9.72
Sensationalism/exaggerations	20	5.56
Confidentiality and collecting information concerns	37	10.28
Others	177	49.17

Finally, in table 4, 360 respondents were directed to a question about the negative effects of social media. They were then given a list of reasons why they believed social media negatively affects their political opinions. They were given multiple response

questions and were able to select as many answers as they agreed on. Most of the respondents believed that social media has a negative effect because of misinformation, made up news, hate, extremism, and harassment garnering 86.94%. 72.22% of the respondents believe that people trust everything who have no idea what to believe. 49.44% of the respondents believe that censorship or bias is a negative downside to social media. These responses are important to consider to better understand how members of the online community, particularly Generation Z, get their news.

Conclusions

It may be inferred that Filipino netizens, particularly generation Z, are frequent social media users. The most popular platforms among generation Z include Facebook, Instagram, Tiktok, YouTube, and Twitter. This explains why politicians must engage with generation Z through popular social media sites to effectively reach them.

The research discovered a prevalent trend among Filipino netizens, particularly the generation Z. First, it is worth noting that the majority of respondents reported checking social media "several times a day". However, most respondents stated that social media negatively impacted their political opinions. Note that, despite most respondents believing that social media has negative effects, they continue to use it many times every day.

This research also revealed a significant result when respondents were asked who they trusted to learn about politics. According to most respondents, family was the most favored option. This evidence refutes the notion that generation Z learns political opinions more through social media than from their parents or professors. It is acceptable to argue that most of our people are becoming more informed and aware of their political participation and process. However, this does not imply that they are not exposed to or recognize social media influencers.

Recommendations

The results of the research suggest that politicians should take a thorough and comprehensive approach to reaching out to Filipino netizens, particularly generation Z. They should develop more effective ways for connecting with more people and encouraging them to participate in politics and support democracy. These are the recommendations based on the data gathered: 1) encourage generation Z to get involved in politics while they are young because it is crucial to the future success of the political system; 2) strengthen the awareness of the importance of political participation among the generation Z; 3) increase the use of social media in promoting political agenda because it is the most widely used platforms for generation Z; 4) minimize the false and misleading information in social media to produce credible and trustworthy information; 5) ensure the accessibility of social media platforms for better communication; 6) and

finally, politicians should increase positive media influence in order to gain positive image and support among the public.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical rules were followed throughout the research process to ensure its integrity and quality. First, the researchers got permission from the university where the survey was carried out. Respondents were then told about the nature, purpose, and use of the data collected for the research. To protect their privacy, they provided their voluntarily informed consent through a signed agreement. If they did not wish to participate in the survey, they could opt out.

Furthermore, respondents were assured of the confidentiality of the data supplied and that completed surveys would be kept and used strictly for academic purposes. Finally, to ensure an impartial conclusion for this research, responses were treated objectively and fairly throughout the data processing procedure.

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